

Neural Network-Based Calibration of Electrical Models for Silicon Carbide Diodes

Mohammed Amira*, Aleš Chvála

Institute of Electronics and Photonics, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava Ilkovičova 3, 812 19 Bratislava, Slovakia

*Xamira@Stuba.sk

Abstract

Silicon carbide (SiC) diodes are crucial in high-power applications due to their excellent electrical and thermal properties. However, the nonlinear nature of SiC diodes is rarely represented by conventional calibration methods. This paper proposes a neural network-based calibration methodology using simulation data for extracting the ideality factor (n), saturation current (I_S), series resistance (R_S), and leakage resistance (R_L), of a diode directly from V-I curves. Implemented as a feedforward network with two hidden layers and optimized hyperparameters, the network takes advantage of the logarithmically scaled training data to enhance the performance in the low-current region. The method shows low mean squared error and mean percentage deviation below 5% for a large operating range and hence can be considered a computationally efficient approach compared to the traditional curve-fitting techniques in SiC diode modelling

Introduction

SiC diodes are necessary in high-power and high-frequency applications because of their high breakdown voltage, low switching losses, and excellent performance in extreme environments [1]. Electrical modelling with accuracy is necessary for their efficiency optimization, but conventional calibration methods, like numerical curve fitting, struggle to capture the nonlinear behaviour of SiC power devices and often require huge computational resources[2].

Neural networks provide a potent alternative by learning complex relationships between input and output characteristics of semiconductor devices[3]. This work proposes a neural network-based calibration technique for SiC diode modelling, based on synthetic data obtained with numerical simulations. A feedforward neural network with two hidden layers is trained to minimize mean squared error, using logarithmic scaling to improve accuracy, in particular in the low-current regime. The proposed approach aims at improving the accuracy in SiC diode modelling with very limited computational complexity. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the computational framework and neural network architecture; results and performance evaluation are reported in Section 3; finally, conclusions and future perspectives are given in Section 4.

Experimental / Computational Details

The proposed study presents a neural network-based approach to the calibration of the electrical model of SiC diodes. The dataset required for training and validation of

the neural network is generated by using the Shockley diode equation in numerical simulations:

$$I_D = I_S \left(e^{\frac{q(V_f - I_D R_s)}{nkT}} - 1 \right) + \frac{V_f}{R_L}$$

Where I_D is the diode current, I_S is the saturation current, V_f is the forward voltage, R_S is the series resistance, R_L is the leakage resistance, n is the ideality factor, q is the electron charge ($1.602 \times 10^{19} C$), k is the Boltzmann constant ($1.38 \times 10^{-23} J/K$), and T is the absolute temperature (300 K). The dataset consists of multiple I-V characteristics simulated across a wide range of parameters, including n values from 1 to 3, I_S ranging from 10^{-13} to 10^{-7} A, R_S spanning 10^{-4} to $10^2 \Omega$, and R_L varying from 10^6 to $10^{15} \Omega$.

A feedforward neural network with two hidden layers was implemented in MATLAB to calibrate the diode model. The input layer receives logarithmically scaled voltage-current (V_f, I_D) data, while the output layer predicts key diode parameters (n, I_S, R_S, R_L). It has 18 neurons for the first hidden layer and 14 for the second layer using the Levenberg-Marquardt backpropagation algorithm for the training process. To get better results, especially for lower current values, a logarithmic scale was used on both the input and output data. The network that is used here is trained on 5000 simulated I-V curves, where the hyperparameters were optimized for minimum MSE. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the neural network architecture.

Figure 1 Neural network architecture for SiC diode parameter extraction

Hidden Layer 1 Neurons (H1)	Hidden Layer 2 Neurons (H2)	Mean Error (%)
5	5	5.72
6	6	5.12
20	18	4.68
19	18	4.68
18	14	2.87
19	14	3.37

Table 1 Table of Neural Network Performance: Mean Percentage Error (%) for Different Configurations of Neurons in the Hidden Layers (H1 and H2), Highlighting the Best Results.

Results in the table prove that model performance heavily depends on the number of neurons in hidden layers. Too small configurations, such as H1=5 and H2=5, give higher errors, but too big also doesn't guarantee the best results. A medium, balanced configuration such as H1=18 and H2=14 gives the lowest error—a moderate number of neurons in each hidden layer turns out to give better overall performance.

Results and discussion

The neural network model was trained with 30 inputs and corresponding output pairs. It was finally trained in 627.29 s. It yielded a mean squared error with a value of 0.81 while the model's mean percentage deviation resulted in 3 %. The percentage error for each of the individual parameters is 2.84 % for the ideality factor n , 0.33% for saturation current I_S , 5.76% for the series resistance R_S , and 3.34% for the leakage resistance R_L . The average total combined percentage error was 2.87%. During validation, the optimized values for I_S , n , R_S , and R_L were found to be 1.22×10^{-12} A, 2.00, 1.00Ω , and $1 \times 10^7 \Omega$, respectively, with an RMSE of 1.53×10^{-8} .

Figure 2 Histogram of Percentage Errors for Diode Model Parameters

These optimized parameters had very negligible percentage errors, hence indicating excellent model performance. Figure 2 shows a histogram of the percentage errors in the estimated parameters, showing the distribution of errors across the different parameters. Figure 3 shows the verification of the diode model fitted log currents (blue line) versus the measured ones (red dots) for different voltages. The close fit of these curves implies

that the neural network estimated the all parameters of the diode, with small errors, hence efficiently modelling the voltage-current characteristic of the system.

Figure 3 Evaluation of the Diode Model: Comparison of Measured (Red Dots) and Fitted (Blue Line) Log Currents as a Function of Voltage, Demonstrating the Accuracy of the Neural Network-Based Parameter Optimization Approach

Conclusions

The neural network calibration for SiC diodes resulted in a very good accuracy with a low MSE of 0.81 and an overall mean error of 2.87% using the optimal configuration of 18 neurons in H1 and 14 in H2. The validation demonstrated very small errors of parameters and an excellent agreement between the measured and fitted log currents, making this approach a very robust and efficient alternative to traditional methods.

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